

FEATURES OF LINGUISTIC GENRE AND INSTRUCTION

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Annotation: *This article devoted to different genres of formal business texts, and all of them have been studied to varying degrees. Currently, the instruction genre is very common, since almost everything sold on the market, every program available for download in online stores and almost every human action in a given situation is accompanied by an instruction that makes our life easier and allows us to achieve what we want. result.*

Key words: *communication, text, instruction, information, document, descriptive, instructive.*

Instruction is an imperative speech genre that aims to inform the addressee of the procedure, methods and rules for the implementation of an action in order to encourage him to do the right thing.

The instruction refers to the texts of the official business functional style, is filled with technical content and has a standardized form. It is aimed at the general public, since the various operating instructions are usually used by a wide range of people in the field of everyday communication. It should be noted that despite the fact that instructions are a genre of business communication, they do not have the status of an official document. The speech genre of instructions includes two types of information - descriptive and instructive[1].

At the beginning of the text of the instruction, a descriptive part is given, which describes the product itself, namely its characteristics, special functions and purpose. This is followed by an instructive part, which provides information on the permissible and impermissible actions regarding the product in question.

The speech genre of "instructions" can be characterized by a variety of types of speech motivation. So, for example, according to scientists, the texts of the genre we are considering can be divided into "instructions" and "non-instructions". The author believes that instructions can be divided into several different groups:

1. Instructions for technical products and various devices, the text of which contains rules of conduct, instructions and an algorithm of actions in various situations (if we are talking, for example, about safety instructions).

2. Depending on the intended addressee, instructions can be divided into narrowly focused guides for specialists in this field and into instructions for a wide range of consumers of various services and goods.

3. Also, instructions can be divided according to the scope into household, medical, industrial, official, military, etc.

4. According to the structural features of the instructions, the author divides the regulated (standard) and non-regulated (non-standard). The latter are distinguished by a creative approach to the organization of the text, an unusual way of presenting information.

5. On a formal basis, the instructions are divided into expanded, detailed brochures, designed to accompany the user throughout the operation of the product, and short guides to action, containing the minimum necessary information (instructions-folds)[2].

Summarizing the above, we can single out the main functions of texts of the instruction genre - informative and regulatory: to familiarize the client with the features of the product and the rules for its safe use.

Among the great variety of genres of texts of the official business style, there is a certain unevenness in the number of studies on the topic of a particular genre. The instruction genre belongs to the second group of the aforementioned genres. In the modern world, this genre is very popular and often used, however, despite this, it is still little explored.

Each speech genre is characterized by its own characteristics, by which one or another genre can be distinguished from others.

The structural qualities of the text of the "instruction" genre include:

- 1) consistency
- 2) connectedness and integrity
- 3) precision
- 4) clarity, understandability, accessibility

Texts of the speech genre "instructions" have a common structure, but unlike other genres of official business style, when compiling texts of the "instructions" genre, some "freedom" in the construction of the text can be allowed, and it is also possible to add your own sections[7].

Below is the most general structure of the studied genre of text:

1. Introduction. In the first part of the text, an appeal to the buyer with gratitude for the purchase of this product is highlighted.
2. The main part. Preparation for work.
3. The final part: maintenance, storage rules, possible malfunctions and methods for their elimination, warranty, warranty card.

Usually, in the instructions, immediately after contacting the buyer, the content is given. It allows the reader to quickly work with the text, helping to quickly find the desired section. Instructions often contain highlighted words (indicators) that draw the reader's attention to important points, for example: WARNING - this instruction describes procedures or conditions that are dangerous to humans if appropriate precautions are not taken.

From the foregoing, we can state the following: the texts of the speech genre of instructions are characterized by grammatical features that help to clearly build the text without confusing the reader, as well as the lack of personal semantics and the desire to make the text as compact as possible, but without losing meaning. Since the instruction genre is the most "free" among other formal business style genres, there is a possibility of deviating from some rules, which does not interfere with distinguishing instructions from texts of other speech genres. Most of the highlighted grammatical features are found in all instructions.

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